

Use of Blog as Mentorship Collaborative Tool Among Library and Information Science Educators in Universities in Bayelsa State, Nigeria

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Abstract

This article focused on Use of Blog as Mentorship Collaborative Tool Among Library and Information Science Educators in Universities in Bayelsa State, Nigeria. The purpose was to examine the relationship between the use of Blog as a collaborative tool and mentorship among LIS educators in Bayelsa State. Descriptive survey design was adopted for the study. The study population and sample size was 25 LIS educators using enumeration sampling technique. The findings revealed that As compared to the benchmark mean of 2.50, the overall mean of 1.44 indicates that the vast majority of respondents do not use Blog App on their mobile devices. The study recommended that mentors and mentees in library and information science programmes should utilize social media platforms or Apps as a collaborative tool for learning; the use of mobile or online mentoring between mentors and mentees, as well as graduate and undergraduate students in library programmes, should be promoted; and, all parties involved in education should fully support and institutionalize the use of collaborative technologies for the development of essential skills.

Keywords: Blog, Collaborative tools, Library and Information Science, Educators, Mentorship, Social Media, Mentor, Mentee, Bayelsa State

Introduction

In recent years, the use of blogs as a mentorship collaborative tool among educators in universities has gained popularity. Blogs have become a valuable platform for sharing knowledge, experiences, and resources among professionals in the field of education. This collaborative approach to mentorship allows

educators to connect with one another, exchange ideas, and provide support and guidance to their peers. In concurrence, Andrade, Lopez & Martin (2009) put forward that teamwork and collaboration have become the vehicles for the integration of knowledge efforts and capabilities for the research process.

Mentorship is a crucial aspect of professional development, especially in the field of Library and Information Science (LIS). With the rapid advancements in technology and the evolving nature of the field, it is essential for educators to stay current and provide guidance to their students. Individuals learn knowledge from one another in a variety of ways, including face-to-face interactions, conversations (verbal and non-verbal) and observations (casual and formal). There are planned mentoring relationships and more casual ones that develop naturally. Some mentees actively seek out certain mentors, while others find their mentors by chance. From Graduate Assistant (GA) to Professor: LIS programmes provide a wide range of career opportunities. Those at lower ranks are expected to pick up knowledge from their superiors, as "publish or perish" is a well-known credo in the academic world. The mentor-mentee relationship thrives when both parties work together toward same goal. Collaboration among LIS educators is based on a shared commitment to solving the issues and overcoming the obstacles that affect all LIS programs. Given its critical role in not just overcoming these obstacles but also advancing LIS education, cooperation has been given considerable attention in the LIS literature. Education in library and information science (LIS) is crucial because it produces LIS professionals of exceptional caliber who play a special role in national progress. When it comes to knowledge, decision-making, and national growth, LIS practitioners are the gatekeepers and brokers of information. Building competent staff is essential for libraries, archives, and information centers to fulfill their mandate of information providing.

When it comes to mentoring, cooperation activities and the usage of collaborative tools are greatly aided by the availability and use of information and communication technology. According to Bajwa and Lewis (2003), cited by Awodoyin, Simiaye, Osisanwo, and Adeyeoye (2020), collaborative technologies cover anything from e-mail to video meetings to proprietary groupware to web-based solutions. Facebook, Twitter, LinkedIn, Blogs, Instant Messaging, Google Drive, Research Gate, Academia, Chat Room, Skype, Google Docs,

Slide Share, Discussion Forum, Voice Mails, Dropbox, Newsletters, Video Mails, Newsgroups, Mailing Lists, Webinars, Listservs, Intranet, Flickr, Web Forum, Microsoft Share Point, Podcasts, and Flipchats. WhatsApp, Instagram, and Telegram are three other collaboration applications that are now popular among librarians and academics.

Collaborative tools are designed to enhance the quality of communication between their users. According to Kreijin and Kirchner (2002), referenced by Awodoyin et al. (2020), the use of collaborative technologies enables an interactive process in which students may construct new knowledge in a social context. Library attempts to stimulate contact with the many users who use various contemporary communication methods, to satisfy their urgent needs and wishes, might benefit from a discussion of a few of the collaboration capabilities provided by the WhatsApp messaging program (Verma and Verma, 2014). Customers may get in touch with an information expert and ask them everything they need to know to complete their scientific study or syllabi-related special projects. In addition to the aforementioned WhatsApp application for library services, there is also selective dissemination that aims to keep users abreast of the scientific developments in their field of expertise; where the definition of users' attributions according to their specializations and research interests, with the aim of informing them of the new vessels for each in his or her field. One component of this service is advising them of upcoming international conferences and symposia.

A blog is an interactive website that may be maintained by a person or a group and has user-generated content such as blog posts, comments, and links. Sodt and Summey (2009) remarked that readers of blogs do not necessarily need to visit the blog page to get the information, since the technology allows RSS feeds that readers may subscribe to. In order to better communicate with their mentees, some mentors utilize this modern tool. To reach people with relevant information no matter where they may be, mentors and mentees utilize blogs for a wide variety of

purposes, including but not limited to: beginning dialogues about different subjects, promoting new resources, utilizing them as a staff newsletter, and serving as a subject guide (King & Brown, 2009). According to Farkas (2007), blogs are a great way for mentors and mentees to stay in touch and share information because they give mentoring a "human face," encouraging both parties to reveal more about themselves and their activities. Websites like WordPress and Blogger provide free blog programs, making it simple to create a blog; you don't need any knowledge of web design to utilize these services (Sodt & Summey, 2009).

According to Blogger (2004), these programs let you to instantly share your views with the world through the Internet whenever the mood strikes. The final advantage is that members may share and discuss information they've developed with one another, which helps strengthen connections and helps leaders keep their positions.

Because of the weight of several responsibilities in the areas of teaching, administration, and community involvement, every LIS educator aspires to achieve the pinnacle of their career as a symbol of professional progress. They are excessively time-consuming, leaving them with little room in their schedules for reading, research, writing, and publishing. No matter how busy LIS educators are, the "publish or perish" mentality of the modern academic world makes it imperative that they participate in research.

Collaborative tools for mentoring in the information age have been made possible by advances in Information and Communication Technology (ICT), which enhance professional training and contribute to the effective learning of skills necessary for enhanced performance. There has been no study of collaborative tools and mentoring among LIS faculty in Bayelsa State's library schools, despite their widespread usage. As far as this author is aware, there is a dearth of empirical research on the topic of mentoring using collaborative technologies among LIS instructors. This research looks at how LIS educators in Bayelsa State use blog for online collaboration and provide one another guidance.

Purpose of the Study

The focus of this research is on Use of Blog as Mentorship Collaborative Tool Among Library and Information Science Educators in Universities in Bayelsa State, Nigeria. The specific aim is to:

1. Examine the relationship between the use of Blog as a collaborative tool and mentorship among LIS educators in Bayelsa State.

Research Question

What is the relationship between the use of Blog as a collaborative tool and mentorship among LIS educators in Bayelsa State?

Research Hypothesis

The following null hypothesis calculated at 0.05 levels will guide the study:

1. There is no significant relationship between the use of blog and mentorship among LIS educators in library schools in Bayelsa State.

Literature Review

Concept of Use of Blog as a Collaborative Tool and Mentorship

Based on the definition provided by Brownstein and Klein (2006), a blog is a website that is often updated with new content, in the form of time-stamped entries called "posts," which are listed in reverse chronological order (most recent post at the top). Blogs include a wide range of topics, from books and reading to education and libraries. Based on their intended use, Altun (2005) divides blogs into the following categories: individual, group, press, project management, library, institution, and education. The information is posted online, and subscribers to the blog will add fresh entries; site visitors may then read these entries and add their own thoughts in the form of comments. While most blogs just have text, some do feature audio, video, and/or photographic content (Wang, 2008). There are several ways in which blogs might improve education since their widespread adoption. They play a crucial part in higher education by

inspiring students to dig deeper into course material. Teachers may utilize a wide variety of assignments as the basis for engaging blog activities. Skills like analysis, creativity, documentation, teamwork, communication, and comparison are the foundation of these exercises (Lamb and Johnson 2006).

Ongo (2018) It's possible that social networking sites and instant messaging apps were the most popular throughout the e-mentoring process since both mentors and mentees use them often in their day-to-day lives. Researchers Todd, Moon, and Langston (2016) corroborated this finding by noting that they instructed mentees and mentors to choose and choose from the available technologies. The survey found that people tended to favor the technology they were previously familiar with. Self-efficacy in relation to a certain technology has been shown to increase both adoption and confidence in that technology's usefulness (Guriting, Chunwen, & Ndu, 2007).

Blog, according to Lilpee (2017), is "a blog or personal diary that is visible on the web." Content management software makes it possible for persons with little to no technical knowledge to update and maintain blogs on a regular basis. Lilpee (2017) pointed out, among other problems, that blogs have their negatives in addition to their positives. Blogs have certain drawbacks as a means of collaboration, including; Most individuals don't have anything particularly intriguing to say, and/or they lack the writing skills necessary to convey their thoughts clearly and concisely. This includes user comments, some of which may be abusive due to the lack of moderation; Blogs are time-consuming to update since new content must be updated often. Some users may find it challenging and time-consuming to publish to or maintain their blogs. Those who are pressed for time, however, won't face this issue. Users may feel lonely if they rely on blogs since there is no face-to-face interaction between them.

Blog and Mentorship

The "usage of social media technologies for information sharing by university library workers in Nigeria" was studied by Osinulu, Nwokeoma,

Ilo, Fagbohun, Adebayo, Idiegbeyan-Ose, and Olawoyin in 2018. This study used a descriptive research strategy. Participants in the research were employed by libraries at 39 different Nigerian universities. One hundred sixty-five (165) responses were chosen at random from thirty-nine (39) academic libraries. The primary method of data gathering was the administration of a standardized questionnaire during the Nigeria Library Association Annual meeting. Descriptive statistics were employed to describe the data, and SPSS was used for statistical analysis. Researchers found that a majority of Nigerian academic library workers ($x=3.28SD = 1.223$) regularly share information using instant messaging apps and social networking sites such as Weblog, WhatsApp, WeChat, LinkedIn, Facebook, Google+, Fortuito, My space, Academia, and Research Gate. The vast majority of librarians ($x=3.07SD = 0.989$) reported using social media to disseminate articles from their personal journals and proceedings from professional conferences to library patrons and other librarians. Poor internet access was also shown to be a barrier to library staff members' usage of social media tools ($x=3.63SD=0.484$) in Nigeria.

Studying how college students interact with and learn through educational blogs was the focus of Khurshid (2019) study. The research method used was a descriptive survey. University students constituted the study's population. The participants in this research were 100 college freshmen, both male and female. A questionnaire and in-depth interviews were utilized to compile the data. Quantitative data was examined using descriptive statistics (frequency and percentages), while qualitative data was evaluated using theme analysis. The study's findings confirmed that students often use blogs for educational resources and for making connections with their peers. Students participated in class discussions by using educational blogs and commenting on topics. Blogs are a great method to expand students' horizons and teach them new things. Educators and students alike might get to know one another better via the medium of educational blogging. Blogs that aid with education are beneficial for both educators and their students. There should

be seminars and awareness campaigns promoting the integration of cutting-edge technology into higher education. Blogs-related courses should be available at the university and college levels. In addition, this research raises awareness among college freshmen regarding the potential of blogs in the classroom.

Methodology

Descriptive survey research was used for this investigation. All 25 academics (Niger Delta University, Amassoma 14 and Federal University, Otuoke 11) from both of Bayelsa State's library schools made up the study's population. A self-structured questionnaire was delivered to the respondents at their respective universities and then collected by the researcher and research assistants. Respondent information was gathered and analyzed to provide answers to research questions and verify or refute predetermined hypotheses. A four-point rating scale, with SA = 4, A = 3, D = 2, and SD = 1, with the mean of $4+3+2+1/4 = 2.50$ serving as the acceptance criteria we used for the analysis.

Nonetheless, the proposed null hypothesis was put to the test at the 0.05 level of significance. Pearson's Product-Moment Correlation Coefficient was used for this purpose (PPMC). The null hypothesis was rejected when the P-value was greater than 0.05, indicating that there is no significant relationship between the two variables; conversely, the null hypothesis was accepted when the P-value was equal to or less than 0.05, indicating that there is a significant relationship between the two variables.

Presentation of Data

n= 25

Designation	Responses	Percentage (%)
Prof/As. Prof? UL&DUL	3	14.9
Senior Lect./Prin. Libn	4	9.5
Lect. I&II/Sn. L & Libn. I	12	13.8
As. Libn. & Libn. II	6	11.8
TOTAL	25	100

Of the respondents, Table 1 reveals that 3 (14.9%) are professors or university librarians, 4 (9.5%) are senior lecturers or principal librarians, 12 (13.8%) are lecturers or senior lecturers and librarians II, and 6 (11.8%) are assistant librarians and librarians.

Demographic distribution of educational qualification

Table 2: Highest Educational Qualification of Respondents

Highest Educational Qualification	Responses	Percentage
Bachelor	=	=
Master	17	68
PhD	8	32

Table 2 shows that out of a total of twenty-five (25) respondents, seventeen (17) (68%) had Master's degrees and eight (8) (32%) hold Doctoral degrees as their highest educational qualifications.

SECTION B:

Research Question 1

What is the relationship between the use of Blog as a collaborative tool and mentorship among LIS educators in Bayelsa State?

Table 4: Blog Use n=25, criterion mean = 2.50

Sn	Statement	SA	A	D	SD	Mean \bar{x}	Rk
1	Blog App is installed in my smartphone	3(12%)	4(16%)	18(72%)	=	1.44	Disagree
2	I can blog/follow blog effectively	2(8%)	5(20%)	18(72%)	=	1.44	Disagree
3	I use blog to keep in touch with colleagues	2(8%)	5(28%)	18(72%)	=	1.44	Disagree
4	I use blog for education and networking	=	7(28%)	18(72%)	=	1.44	Disagree
5	I use blog for communication with my mentor/mentee	7(28%)	=	18(72%)	=	1.44	Disagree
6	I use blog for electronic document delivery	7(28%)	=	18(72%)	=	1.44	Disagree

Grand mean 1.44

Table 4 shows that the vast majority of respondents agreed with the statements "I have the Blog App on my smartphone" (18/72), "I can blog/follow blog effectively" (18/72), "I use blog to keep in touch with colleagues" (18/72), "I use blog for education and networking" (18/72), "I use blog to communicate with my mentor/mentee" (18/72), and "I use blog for electromotive purposes" (18/72). As compared to the benchmark mean of 2.50, the overall mean of 1.44 indicates that the vast majority of respondents do not use Blog App on their mobile devices. If a user gives this signal, it suggests they

are not interested in using Blog as a mentoring tool for their education. The results show that LIS educators in Bayelsa State have a below-average amount of success when it comes to using blogs as a mentoring tool.

Hypothesis

There is no significant relationship between the use of blog and mentorship among LIS educators in library schools in Bayelsa State.

Table 5: Blog and Mentorship relationship

Variable	N	Mean	Df	t-cal	t-criti	Sig/lev	p-value	Decision
Blog	18	1.48	24	0.102	14.51	0.05	0.001	Sig
Mentorship	25	1.48						

Among LIS teachers at Bayelsa State library schools, Table 5 shows the correlation between blogging and mentoring. The p-value in the table is 0.001 and the computed t-value is t-less than the t-critical value of 14.51 by 0.102. The p-value is smaller than the critical threshold of 0.05 for testing the hypothesis. This suggests that LIS educators at Bayelsa State's library schools cannot find any correlation between blogging and mentoring. Thus, there is no strong correlation between Blog usage and mentoring among LIS

professors in Bayelsa State's various library schools.

Discussion of the Findings

The results of the study are discussed here, along with any conclusions that may be drawn from the researcher's point of view and the cited literature.

Relationship between Blog as a collaborative tool and mentorship among LIS educators in Bayelsa State

Analysis of the data for the first study question showed that the majority of respondents do not have a Blog App loaded on their smartphones, with a grand mean of 1.44 (less than the criteria mean of 2.50). If a user gives this signal, it suggests they are not interested in using Blog as a mentoring tool for their education. The results show that LIS educators in Bayelsa State have a below-average amount of success when it comes to using blogs as a mentoring tool.

Lilpee (2017) corroborates this conclusion by noting that despite their benefits, blogs do have drawbacks. One drawback of blogging as a collaborative tool is that most individuals don't have anything particularly fascinating to say, and/or they lack the writing skills necessary to express their thoughts clearly and concisely.

The results of Omotunde, Fagun, Aderole, and Abidoye (2014), which reveal a substantial correlation between the use of blogs and the academic success of future teachers, are corroborated by these data. Thus, it is important for teachers to include blogging into their curricula. Hence, it is officially declared that the usage of Blog as a collaborative medium and mentoring among LIS instructors in Bayelsa State is growing.

Conclusion

The study's results suggest that in the modern age of information-based education, mentors and mentees alike may benefit from using the collaborative tools provided by applications like WhatsApp, Facebook, Email, Instagram, and Blogs. The research questions asked and answered, as well as the null hypotheses examined, indicate that there is a substantial association between mentoring and the variables analyzed (Blog) among LIS instructors in library schools in Bayelsa State. Based on the findings and data presentation in accordance with the analyzed research questions and tested formulated null hypothesis, it is concluded that there is a positive, significant, and encouraging relationship between the use of collaborative

tools and mentorship among LIS educators in Bayelsa State.

Recommendation

The study's findings informed the following recommendations:

1. Mentors and mentees in library science programs should utilize social media platforms or Apps as a collaborative tool for learning.
2. The use of mobile or online mentoring between mentors and mentees, as well as graduate and undergraduate students in library programmes, should be promoted.
3. All parties involved in education should fully support and institutionalize the use of collaborative technologies for the development of essential skills.

Contribution to Knowledge

This study on the use of blog as collaborative tool and mentoring practices in Bayelsa State's library schools makes a significant addition to the field of Library and Information Science (LIS). In conducting this study, the researcher looked for previous studies on the same topic or ones that were related but came up with very few ones on the Internet and in a few university libraries in the South-South region of the nation. This piece of work will address this problem.

With this research, LIS educators in Bayelsa State may raise awareness among their institution's administration, teachers, and students about the many online collaboration tools that have proven useful in the field. The results of the research will help them realize that we now live in a digital era where technology can be used to greatly improve both individual and group education.

Students and other scholars who conduct future studies related to this one will find this work to be an invaluable resource. It will supplement the primary source material they already have.

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